

Student Inclusion as an Institutional Focus: Report and Implementation of Support Strategies for Educating a Visually Impaired Student in an Engineering Program

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14060941>

Abstract

The inclusion practice in universities is a crucial aspect of enriching the academic experience for all students, regardless of their backgrounds, abilities, or individual characteristics. In this context, this article reports on the inclusion experience of a visually impaired student in an Engineering program at the Mauá Institute of Technology, highlighting the psycho-pedagogical practices and approaches used to promote his full participation. During the inclusion experience, the role of the Mauá Student Support Program (MSSP) was understood as a fundamental element throughout the entire process, as it facilitated an effective interface among the student, professors, and psychologists. A significant example of this collaboration is demonstrated through the interaction between MSSP initiatives and the General Mechanics course, which utilized specially developed didactic materials to engage the student in the context and practices of the discipline. In this work, the MSSP methodology is detailed, covering mentoring and psycho-pedagogical support practices, as well as the action plan that was implemented in the General Mechanics course based on the professors' experiences. The results highlight the effectiveness of MSSP practices, the successful adaptation of didactic materials, and the constructive interactions between the student and the professionals involved, all contributing to the student's positive perception of the inclusion process. This report recognizes that a systemic approach to integrating psychology with other disciplines promotes inclusion and fosters a collaborative educational environment.

Keywords: Student Inclusion; Psycho-pedagogical Practices; Adapted Teaching Materials.

1 Introduction

Including students with disabilities in higher education has emerged as an issue of significant importance, both nationally in Brazil and internationally, driven by legislative milestones and historical advances in promoting inclusive educational rights. The National Education Guidelines and Bases Law and the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 2006, represent legal milestones reinforcing the commitment to educational inclusion. Inclusion becomes even more critical with the growing demands for a more equitable society and the recognition of diversity as a fundamental pillar of social and economic development (Brasil, 1996; ONU, 2006). Additionally, social movements and public policies have promoted the search for more inclusive education, recognizing the importance of diversity in enriching the academic environment and providing equal opportunities (UNESCO, 2019). Within this context, including visually impaired students in undergraduate courses is challenging due to the physical, technological and social barriers that can limit their full participation (Sales & Torres, 2022).

The inclusion of these students in engineering courses presents both challenges and unique opportunities. On the one hand, issues related to the accessibility of teaching materials, laboratories, and physical spaces can represent significant obstacles to the entire academic development of these students (Silva & Pimentel, 2021). On the other hand, engineering offers opportunities to apply innovative and technological solutions to overcome these challenges and promote more effective inclusion (Zanatta & Silva, 2021). Hodges, Roncesvalles, and Kwan (2019) point out the importance of adapting teaching practices to promote the

inclusion of these students in academic engineering environments. Furthermore, studies indicate the need for an interdisciplinary approach involving psychology and teaching professionals to ensure their academic success and social integration (Ciantelli & Leite, 2022; Holanda et al., 2021).

In this context, professional assistance from psychologists emerges as an important resource in supporting the inclusion, permanence, and accessibility of students in undergraduate programs. Collaboration between psychologists and professors enables the identification of individual needs, the development of personalized support strategies, and the monitoring of the inclusion process (Martinez, 2009). Integrating psychopedagogical approaches with educational practices can enhance the effectiveness of interventions and promote a more welcoming and inclusive academic environment for all students, not just those who need specific adaptations, facilitating their academic participation and personal and professional development. Applying psychology in the university context involves navigating a complex network of interpersonal and subjective relationships. This demands both theoretically based and ethical interventions to support the development of everyone involved, including teachers, students, and the institution itself.

The Mauá Student Support Program (MSSP) plays a central role in promoting student inclusion at the University Center of the Mauá Institute of Technology (UN-MIT), a private higher education institution (HEI) in southeastern Brazil. By establishing a practical interface between teachers, students and professionals in the psychological field, MSSP enables the implementation of personalized support and monitoring strategies and assumes the role of giving visibility to students' demands and subjectivities in order to design individual and/or collective actions based on these needs (Mello, Caldeira, & da Matta, 2022).

The UN-MIT offers a concrete example of the benefits of this collaborative approach, specifically by including a visually impaired student in the General Mechanics course taught to all Engineering majors. In this case, cooperation between professionals resulted in successful re-adaptation methodologies and teaching materials previously developed at the same HEI, especially for a subject that develops technical drawing skills (Todaro and Lebrão, 2023a, 2023b). Throughout this article, we aim to explore these themes in more detail, presenting concrete evidence and an in-depth analysis of the challenges and opportunities associated with including a visually impaired student in an undergraduate Engineering program. Finally, this article explores and analyzes the importance and challenges of implementing effective inclusion strategies in the context.

2 Method

A qualitative methodological approach was adopted to achieve the objectives outlined in this study (Bogdan & Biklen, 2007; Patton, 2015), focusing on participant observation and the analysis of documents and reports pertinent to the context of the inclusion of a visually impaired student in the Engineering program at the University Center of the Mauá Institute of Technology (UN-MIT). Through participant observation, the researchers were able to immerse themselves in the daily practices of the Mauá Student Support Program (MSSP), systematically recording the interactions among the student, teachers and psychologists.

Additionally, documents such as MSSP monitoring reports adapted teaching materials used in the General Mechanics course and records of planning meetings among teachers, students and psychology professionals were analyzed. This approach allowed for an in-depth understanding of the strategies employed to promote inclusion and the student's full participation in the academic environment and provided an evaluation of the results. In this work, the student is Pedro (fictitious name), a 22-year-old regular student in the Engineering program, and classified by Brazilian Ministry of Health (2008) as a visually impaired person, since he has had low vision since his childhood.

2.1 Mauá Student Support Program

The Mauá Student Support Program (MSSP) was designed based on best practices and protocols developed in the university environment and the expertise of professionals. MSSP is essential in fostering students' academic success and well-being by offering various services. It is staffed by two psychologists and two teachers from the foundation year of the Engineering program. The staff is responsible for providing emotional support to students, creating a safe and confidential environment to discuss psychological issues, develop coping skills, and facilitate their adaptation, integration, and permanence. It includes counseling on academic, social and personal issues. Furthermore, it fosters close collaboration with other services and professionals at the institution to ensure a comprehensive and integrated approach to student support. By offering multifaceted and personalized support, MSSP plays a crucial role in strengthening the academic community and promoting the success of all students.

The Support, Permanence and Accessibility Center (SPAC), as a complement to MSSP, actively identifies students in need of initiatives for inclusion and equal opportunities initiatives. It conducts academic and socioemotional monitoring and maps their various diagnoses to adapt pedagogical strategies and teaching accessibility. It involves parents, legal guardians, and health professionals setting up a support network when necessary.

2.2 Pedagogical actions

General Mechanics course aims to develop skills inherent in the analysis of dynamic systems, and it does so by applying fundamental concepts and models of the kinematics and dynamics of material points and rigid bodies (França & Matsumura, 2011). For this reason, the course proposes studying a series of plane and spatial mechanisms, each with its specific purpose. The academic staff chose to offer students the reproduction of mechanical systems using printed models and to incorporate them, with procedural adaptations, into the tactile module made by Todaro and Lebrão (2023a), due to the objects of analysis proposed by the course are presented to undergraduates using either illustrations or graphic representations.

Before discussing the methodology used, it is important to point out that Todaro and Lebrão (2023a, 2023b) proposed tactile modules as tools for students participating in the Technical Drawing class at the same Higher Education Institution (HEI), which was offered in a competency-based format (Todaro & Lebrão, 2022). These devices were made according to recommendations suggested by Duarte (2004a, 2004b), Almeida, Santos, et al. (2017) and Fucks (2018). Specific details can be found on the works written by Todaro and Lebrão (2023a, 2023b); but, in a general way, the establishment of relationships between pins and cords in the spatial domain of a module, which reproduces technical drawing meshes using calibrated holes, is the foundational principle for using tactile materials. The module was used as a Cartesian reference for analyzing both flat and three-dimensional mechanisms, even though the subject of General Mechanics does not require students to tactilely map standardized contours.

Therefore, the tactile modules accommodated the mechanisms proposed during face-to-face classes, ensuring they were similar to the models presented through conventional illustrations. Thus, the experience offered to the student involved sensory perception of the mechanism and reproduction of the associated movement. This means that the model not only allowed the referred student to tactically perceive the contours of the proposed system but also enabled him to reproduce the typical movements of the mechanisms referenced. Figure 1 illustrates the model used to reproduce the operation of a planar mechanism in one of the classes, aiming to develop mathematical models that can predict the kinematic parameters of a material point moving along a linear guide. In this case, the functions defining the trajectory of the material point and the sliding speed of an arm attached to a horizontal guide were known.

Similarly, Figure 2 depicts a model created to reproduce a three-dimensional mechanism used when investigating mechanisms involving relative movement between components. This model is specifically designed to discuss about kinematic parameters of a mobile component that moves at a constant speed along the guide and couples to an element rotating at a constant angular speed. The mechanisms attached to the tactile module are not fixed; they are designed to allow students to study them in different configurations.

Illustration of the mechanism studied

Reproduction of the mechanism in a tactile module

Figure 1. A two-dimensional model capable of reproducing the movement of a material point in a rectilinear trajectory is constructed under the influence of a guide attached to a horizontal reference

Illustration of the mechanism studied

Reproduction of the mechanism in a tactile module

Figure 2. A three-dimensional model capable of reproducing the movement of a body about a guide attached to a rotating structure is constructed

The examples presented are part of a set of experiences designed to bring visually impaired students closer to the practices proposed by the course. Therefore, the timely availability of teaching materials in face-to-face classes was the alternative found for students to develop specific skills in an environment based on their autonomy.

3 Results

The presence of a visually impaired student prompted discussions among the Mauá Student Support Program staff, the teachers, and the student himself, instigating a reflection on adapting teaching practices. This context has started to review paradigms and premises related to teaching the exact sciences. Traditionally, these have relied on a single method of transmitting knowledge and abstract physics concepts through visual resources.

The MSSP is committed to monitoring all students who need adaptation and accessibility. Additionally, the teachers also carry out this monitoring, which allows them to engage positively with the student. Students are individuals in development, full of desires and potential. Even in the face of possible limitations such as visual impairment, they need support to stay on their chosen career path and achieve an excellent academic education.

In order to cultivate an environment that is both welcoming and inclusive, we conducted initial interviews to gain insights into the student's academic history, past experiences in school (both positive and negative), familiarity with technological resources, social skills, level of autonomy and independence, emotional considerations related to their disability, and support from family members and external professionals, among other relevant factors. It is essential to know the student's background in order to understand their limitations and potential.

As such, it is essential to note that since childhood, Pedro has had consistent family support that projects him as a person with only one physical limitation: low vision. Pedro was not literate in Braille and did not use a stick to get around, factors that do not reduce his autonomy. In addition, he has had professionals throughout his life who have stimulated his ability to interpret curves and shapes, giving him positive accuracy in terms of his spatial ability. He has previous training in economics and shows a facility for understanding and performing mathematics.

Considering Pedro's previous experiences, such as suitable stimuli throughout his life and a previous degree, his initiative and proactivity in the face of challenges are visible. He communicates what he needs and tells us what changes need to be made so that he can get it done - the staff's primary concern. In addition, his spatial representation is preserved. This information was fundamental to creating a diagnostic assessment of the student's needs and, mainly, establishing rapport and building a bond of trust between the student and the institution, essential for an environment conducive to a student-centered teaching-learning process.

The next step involved meetings with the professors before classes began, during which the students' abilities and resources were shared, inviting the professors to experiment with different teaching approaches to meet individual learning needs better. The teachers could creatively and qualitatively expand the technical and pedagogical resources available for teaching their subjects based on the content to be taught and the student's physical and cognitive abilities. The literature suggests this is the path to inclusion (Ciantelli & Leite, 2022; Sales & Torres, 2022; Silva & Pimentel, 2021; Zanata & Silva, 2021). Adaptation is not just about modifying existing instruments to provide a "new form of visualization" but about creating resources that enable learning through other sensory capacities, such as touch and hearing.

The leading assistive technologies and digital literacy for visually impaired students in higher education are pointed out in the literature, including the 3D printer, and encourage the search for continuous improvements in adaptation (Tamy et al., 2022). This study used the tactile module to reproduce the piece, an assistive technology with little academic backing. The staff's biggest concern is getting the student to do what is proposed. To address this, they must identify the best way for the student to implement it, considering their abilities and limitations. In the same way, the service provided by MSSP puts the student at the centre and assesses with them what adaptations and needs are required.

Although using visual aids has historically been a common practice and recognized as a quality pedagogical support, the shift to an educational approach centered on the student and their integral skills, which are not

limited to visual acuity, raises questions about this practice. It was possible to identify new communication strategies between teacher and student, resulting in a satisfactory teaching and learning process by adopting an approach that starts from the concepts to be taught and considers the student's abstraction and knowledge absorption conditions.

The experience demonstrated a demand for voluntary training of professionals and for careful didactic-pedagogical actions given the expectations of those involved regarding the student's adaptation and success. Throughout the process, it became clear that forming a collective, multidisciplinary initiative aims to enhance the student's practical learning and inclusion in the university environment. In this way, the use of the materials developed by Todaro and Lebrão (2023a, 2023b), adapted for the study of planar and spatial mechanisms, enabled the student to be included in the context of the General Mechanics course, with no discernment compared to students with normal vision.

From a technical point of view, the visually impaired student had ample contact with the suggested systems and was not limited to descriptions but also had the opportunity to simulate the movement inherent in each mechanism he was asked to analyze. Additionally, it is worth noting that the student successfully associated terms from specific mathematical models more efficiently when we made the tactile model available while using the materials. However, it can be inferred that the student has developed his specific skills with the help of the teaching materials; however, he manifests them independently of these devices.

Another point observed was the openness of the subject professor, who was incredibly dedicated to evaluating and building materials in the HEI's laboratories. In addition, the institution provided the student with the exclusive assistance of a monitor to support the inclusion process. Throughout the year, the student often expressed the need for academic monitors only on specific occasions, such as the application of assessment activities and when it was necessary to manipulate multiple objects simultaneously.

Overall, the process conducted between the MSSP professionals, and the teaching staff was positive in emotional terms, demonstrating the effectiveness of a collaborative, student-centered approach to promoting the inclusion and academic development of students with special needs. The belief is that the alignment the MSSP coordinators made with the student, the support monitor, the psychologists, the academic staff, and the institution's administrative staff was the difference in effectively achieving inclusion.

Although the report presented here was a positive and successful experience, it is essential to note that the path is one of trial and error. Experiments that are not successful are often not published and shared, but they must be validated similarly. This shows how actively advancing new technologies for inclusion can gain visibility and enhance the quality of teaching. In addition, there is an expectation from those involved that the student will adapt and succeed. It is necessary to be trained, think and act differently, and look for tools and studies that have already dealt with these adaptations to provide a solution that facilitates the student's learning.

4 Conclusion

This article aims to present evidence on the barriers and challenges related to integrating a visually impaired student into an Engineering program, assisted by a team that included psychologists and professors. It is an action carried out in a complementary way.

Therefore, people with special educational needs must overcome the representation based on incapacity, inefficiency and unproductivity. It is the role of the HEI and its staff to find ways of fostering the development of student's skills and abilities. In this case, the MSSP-student-professor relationship stands out as successful in adapting and promoting educational practices.

Ultimately, the primary objective of this process is to empower students with the tools they need to achieve autonomy, quality of life and social inclusion, thus promoting a significant transformation in their educational

journey. Future studies and applications must consider these aspects as fundamental foundations for developing inclusive and effective practices in the university environment and society.

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